

ON THE NATURE OF THE ELECTRIC CHARGE OF A PRECIPITATE FORMED IN PRESENCE OF AN EXCESS OF EITHER OF ITS CONSTITUENT IONS.

PART I.

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In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 670) it has been shown that the nature of the electric charge of a ferrocyanide precipitate, formed from the precipitants, when they are equivalent or one in excess of another, shows that when the concentration of the electrolytes taken is 0.1N, the charge of copper and uranium ferrocyanide is always positive, while that of zinc ferrocyanide is negative but when the concentration is 0.01N, the charge of copper ferrocyanide is always negative. From this it would appear that the nature of the charge of a precipitate depends on

(i) the nature of the electrolytes taken for precipitation of a particular precipitate and also on, (ii) the concentrations of the electrolytes taken and (iii) is independent of the sequence of mixing, i.e., whether an electrolyte MN is added to another PQ or the latter added to the former.

These results are apparently not in agreement with the observations of Lotter Moser on silver halides (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1905, ii, 72, 39; Lotter Moser and Lothe, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 62, 359), of Fajans (*ibid.*, 1921, 27, 478) and of Mukherjee and his co-workers on silver iodide and other systems (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 335; 1924, 1, 173) who found that a slight excess of one of the precipitating electrolytes imparts a charge to the precipitate (silver halide) similar to that of the ion, common to the precipitate and one of the electrolytes taken for precipitation.

Recently however Verwey (*Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 16, 363) has reported the work of Julien in which it has been shown that silver halides do not always acquire the same charge as that of the constituent ion present in excess. Moreover, in our work (*loc. cit.*) it has been shown that the nature of the charge appears to depend on the initial concentrations and the nature of the electrolytes taken for precipitation. This difference as has been pointed out before (*loc. cit.*), is due to a difference in the nature and the method of preparation of the precipitates to start with. In our experiments, the measurements of cataphoretic velocity were done just at and after the time of precipitation, while in the experiments done by other authors, the starting

material was pure, *i.e.*, free from electrolytes. Hence it was thought desirable to re-investigate the nature of the charge in the case of these and other precipitates under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Since the point, raised above is cleared up if the nature of the electric charge acquired by the precipitate is known, only the sign of the charge of different precipitates has been measured by the micro-cataphoretic method (*cf.* Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 370; Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Sen-gupta, *ibid.*, 1936, 13, 428). The following tables contain the experimental results obtained with different precipitates.

TABLE I.

Copper ferrocyanide.

CuSO_4 and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$, 50 c.c. each.

Excess of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ (N/10).	(Former added to latter).			Excess of CuSO_4 (N/100).	(Latter added to former).		
	Charge after Pptn.	2½ hrs.	20 hrs.		Charge after Pptn.	3 hrs.	22 hrs.
0 c.c.	+	+	+	0	-	-	-
0.5	+	+	+	0.5	-	-	-
1	+	+	-(feeble)	1	~ (feeble)	-	-
2	+	+(feeble)	-	2	0	±	+
3	-(feeble)	-	-	3	-(feeble)	+	+
4	-	-	-	5	+	+	+
5	-	-	-				

TABLE II.

Zinc ferrocyanide. $ZnSO_4$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, 50 c.c. each.

(Latter added to former).			(Latter added to former).		
Excess of $ZnSO_4$ (N/10).	Charge after Pptn.	20 hrs.	Excess of $ZnSO_4$ (N/100).	Charge after Pptn.	48 hr.
0 c. c.	-	-	0 c. c.	-	-
0.5	-	-	5	-	-
1	-	-	10	-	-
3	-	-	12	-	-
5	- (feeble)	-	14	-	-
8	- (")	-	18	-	-
10	- (")	-	25	0	-
12	+ (")	+			
15	+ (")	+			

TABLE III.

Uranium ferrocyanide. $UO_2(NO_3)_2$, $6H_2O$ and $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, $3H_2O$, 50 c.c. each.

(Former added to latter).			(Latter added to former).		
Excess of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ (N/10).	Charge after Pptn.	48 hr.	Excess of $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ (N/100).	Charge after Pptn.	20 hr.
0 c. c.	+	+	0 c. c.	-	-
0.5	+	+	10	-	-
5	+	+	15	-	-
10	+	+	20	-	-
12	0	+	25	-	-
15	+	+	20	-	-
			25	-	- (feeble)
			35	- (feeble)	+ (feeble)

TABLE IV.

Silver Iodide.

AgNO ₃ and KI, 50 c.c. each (Latter added to former).			AgNO ₃ and KI, 50 c.c. each (Latter added to former).		
Excess of AgNO ₃ (N/10).	Charge after Pptn.	20 hrs.	Excess of AgNO ₃ (N/100).	Charge after Pptn.	21 hrs
0 c. c.	—	—	0 c. c.	—	—
0.5	+	—	0.5	+	—
1	+	—	1	+	—
2	+	+	2	+	+
5	+	+			
10	+	+			

TABLE V.

*Silver Iodide.*AgNO₃ and KI, 50 c.c. each (latter added to former).

Excess of KI (N/10).	Charge after precipitation.	Charge after 22 hrs.
0 c. c.	—	—
0.5	—	—
1	—	—
2	—	—

DISCUSSION.

The reaction between copper sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide is represented by

Here we have the copper ferrocyanide precipitate and in solution potassium sulphate. When the concentrations of the precipitating electrolytes are high (here N/10), the initial charge is always positive (even if copper

sulphate is added to potassium ferrocyanide, in which case, the chance of the precipitate being negatively charged is greater) when the electrolytes taken for precipitation are equivalent or even when excess of potassium ferrocyanide [0.5 c.c. of $N/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$ in a total volume of 100 c.c.] is taken. With excess of higher and higher concentrations of potassium ferrocyanide, the charge is initially positive but becomes negative with time until at an excess of 3 c.c. of $N/10\text{-K}_4\text{Fe(CN)}_6$, the charge is negative from the very beginning. At this ($N/10$) and higher concentrations of the precipitation electrolytes when mixed in equivalent quantities the charge of the precipitate is always positive, irrespective of the method of addition (*cf.* Part II, *loc. cit.*).

If, however, the precipitate is formed from dilutions of electrolytes in equivalent quantities (here taken $N/100$), the charge is negative irrespective of the method of addition of the two electrolytes (*cf.* Part II, *loc. cit.*). Here the precipitate remains negative even in excess of copper sulphate (1 c.c. of CuSO_4 in a total volume of 100 c.c.) but with still higher concentrations of copper sulphate the charge becomes neutral and then positive. At an excess of 2 c.c. (CuSO_4 , $N/100$), the time effect is apparent (*cf.* Table I). In order to explain these results, it would be necessary to refer briefly to the theories on the origin of the charge of such precipitates. This mechanism of the origin of the charge of the precipitate or of the primary or initial formation of the double layer was first clearly given by Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103) and later on slightly modified by Lange (*cf.* Verwey, *loc. cit.*, Lange and Berger, *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1930, 36, 171).

In a way, there is no fundamental distinction between the two ideas about the formation of the double layer. Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) starts from the chemical point of view and assumes that due to residual unbalanced chemical affinity on the surface of a precipitate, one of the constituent ions will be adsorbed during the precipitation thus imparting a definite magnitude and sign of the charge on the individual particles in the precipitate. In presence of excess of one of the constituent ions (*i.e.* to say, the ion fitting in the lattice of the crystal), the particular ion should be primarily adsorbed by the precipitate in preference to other ions present in the solution. Due to the charge so acquired, ions of opposite sign will be attracted near the surface. Some of these ions are mobile and free, others are bound, only the latter being effective in diminishing the surface density of charge. Lange assumes that the primary formation of the double layer is due to a difference in the thermodynamic potential of an ion in the lattice and in the solution. In the case of silver halides, he assumes that the metallic ions (*i.e.* silver)

would pass from the solid phase to the solution. Since the solubility product of the halide is constant, some of the halide ions must be precipitated from the solution to the solid phase. Thus silver halides in contact with pure water must be negative as is also experimentally found to be case, and also the precipitate when initially formed should take up more halide ions than silver for the same reason and thus be negatively charged. According to Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*), the precipitate should have the charge of that constituent ion of the precipitate which is present in excess at the time of precipitation, and the electric density of charge of a precipitate *thus should not depend on the concentrations* of the precipitating electrolytes. According to Lange (*loc. cit.*) the charge of the precipitate *should not also depend on the concentrations* of the precipitating electrolytes when they are taken in equivalent quantities. According to both the theories, when a solution of potassium ferrocyanide is added to copper sulphate, the copper ferrocyanide is formed always in an excess of copper sulphate, and therefore the precipitate should be positively charged, whereas in the reverse way of mixture, the charge should be negative. The facts stated above are not in agreement with the conclusions drawn from these theories.

It is true, according to Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*), that the presence of a concentrated solution of K_2SO_4 , may make the charge of the copper ferrocyanide positive, and when the precipitate is formed in a more dilute solution, the concentration of K_2SO_4 is low and is thus not sufficient to reverse the negative charge of the precipitate formed. For this, we have to assume that the initial charge of the copper ferrocyanide precipitate is negative under all conditions and subsequent secondary adsorption of potassium ions modifies the charge depending of course on the concentration of potassium ions present at the time of, and after precipitation. According to the theories stated above, the charge of a precipitate is not independent of the method of addition of the precipitating electrolytes, and cannot therefore be always initially negative. The considerations set forth above are valid only when the precipitating electrolytes are taken in equivalent quantities. If either of the precipitating electrolytes is in excess, then of course, the non-agreement of facts with derivations from these theories is still more apparent. Data on uranium ferrocyanide precipitate (*cf.* Table III), show the same peculiarities as copper ferrocyanide, and support the conclusions drawn above. A precipitate of zinc ferrocyanide shows a negative charge even in a considerable excess of zinc sulphate (*cf.* Table II), a fact which is difficult to reconcile with the postulations of Mukherjee (which have been fruitful in explaining so many facts observed by others, *loc. cit.*) unless of course it is assumed

that subsidiary chemical reactions play a part. It follows that zinc ions should have been adsorbed due to residual chemical affinity on the surface of zinc ferrocyanide (here zinc is divalent and ferrocyanide tetravalent) and the charge should have been positive; from Lange's theory it follows that in presence of moderate amounts of zinc ions in solution, thermodynamic considerations demand that zinc ion should not have been discharged on the surface of the zinc ferrocyanide and the charge should be thus negative. At higher concentrations, there is a probability (rather remote) of the charge being positive as we actually find. But the fact, that the charge of a precipitate depends, at least in some cases, on the concentrations of the precipitants, goes definitely against the theory of thermodynamic potentials of these ions as the cause of the primary formation of double layer.

So is also the case with silver iodide. Here the concentration effect is absent, *i.e.*, whether silver iodide is precipitated from $N/100\text{-AgNO}_3$ and $N/100\text{-KI}$ or from $N/10\text{-AgNO}_3$ and $N/10\text{-KI}$, the charge is always negative, when the precipitants are mixed in equivalent quantities. With slight excess of silver nitrate, the charge, though initially positive, becomes negative afterwards with time. With still higher excess of silver nitrate, the charge is always positive. At the time of our investigations we were not aware of the somewhat similar result obtained by Julien (*cf.* Verwey. *loc. cit.*). It is not apparent from that paper whether the precipitates of silver halides were washed free from all electrolytes and then kept in contact with low concentrations of AgNO_3 and then the charge of the precipitate measured or the charge of the freshly formed precipitate in contact with potassium nitrate (formed as a result of the reaction) was measured, as we have done. It will appear that the initial positive charge, presumably due to the primary adsorption of silver ions which are present in excess, is modified and becomes negative with time—a fact which again contradicts the fundamental assumptions of the current theories.

Verwey's (*loc. cit.*) elaboration of Lange's idea on the primary formation of double layer, depending on the thermodynamic potentials of the ions adsorbed and a shift of the zero point of the total potential, does not lead us any further, for *the shift of the zero point* does not evidently depend on the concentrations of the *precipitating electrolytes taken*.

It would appear, however, that the initial charge of these precipitates depends in addition to residual chemical affinity of the surface and to some extent the thermodynamic potential of the constituent ions on their crystalline or jelly-like structure. Thus if Mukherjee's theory be elaborated in the

sense that in addition to residual chemical affinity of the surface, adsorption of ions also depends on their thermodynamic potentials and on the crystalline structure of the adsorbent, then there might be possible explanations of all the facts observed. These ideas were explicit though not implicitly stated (*cf.* Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). Thus during the formation of the precipitate, it acquires an initial charge which is gradually modified due to the adsorption of a number of ions from the solution and with time when equilibrium is obtained, the precipitate finally acquires a definite magnitude and sign of the charge depending on the concentration of the particular ions present at and after the time of precipitation on the structure of the adsorbent. No definite picture can be given of such processes (which appear to be characteristic by themselves) unless their crystalline structure is completely known and further experimental work on other systems is available. All that can be said is that, each and every precipitate has its own characteristic properties, which depends *mainly on the history of its preparation.*

S U M M A R Y.

1. A polar precipitate does not show the same sign of the charge as the constituent ion present in moderate excess at the time of precipitation.

2. There is a time effect on the density of the charge, *i.e.*, the sign of the charge changes with time, sometimes when the precipitants are taken in equivalent quantities and sometimes when one of the precipitant is present in large excess.

3. The sign of the charge appears to depend on the concentrations of the precipitants taken, and independent of the sequence of mixing.

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